

INFLUENCE OF TRIMMING PROCESS ON THE SURFACE QUALITY AND ON THE MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF CFRP STRUCTURES

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1 Introduction

Trimming is the first machining operation performed on composite structures after demoulding. However, the anisotropy and the highly heterogeneous nature of composite materials make their machinability very complex. In addition, regardless of the machining process used (conventional or non-conventional) the phenomenon of the removal of material is followed by the appearance of damaged zones. This can lead to the non-respect of the machining quality (according to imposed industrial standards). These damaged areas are located on the free edges of the machined surface (uncut fibres/flaking/delamination) and/or on the machined surface (uncut fibres, thermal and/or mechanical degradation of the matrix) [1,2]. When machining is conducted with a cutting tool such as in the case of conventional machining, the defects localized at the free edges are mainly influenced by the cutting forces. These forces are strongly affected by the cutting tool's geometry, the cutting parameters, the tool wear, etc. Concerning the damages located on the machined surface, they are mainly affected by the relative angle between the cutting speed direction and the fibre direction of the machined composite material, the cutting parameters and also by the wear of the cutting tool [1,2].

In order to better understand the phenomenon behind the emergence of these damages and the different mechanisms leading to their creation, various research works have been carried out. These studies which are mainly based on the orthogonal cutting [3-

5] have shown that damages due to machining are mainly influenced by the relative angle (Θ) measured between the cutting speed direction and the fibres orientation. In this case, the maximum damage is observed when this angle (Θ) is at -45° and 90° . In addition, the severity of these defects increases with the increase of the wear of the cutting tool [2, 6-10], that is why, tools made of diamond and carbide, are highly recommended for machining composite materials [1].

Different works in the literature have mentioned that, the generated defects are strongly related to the fibres' direction [2-9]. This result is well observed during the orthogonal cutting [3-5]. The propagation of the delamination with the increasing of the tool wear is commonly observed during the drilling of composite materials [10-13]. Based on previous works [14-16], the fibre content and the manufacturing process of the composite part have an important influence on quality of the machined surface.

In order to reduce damages during trimming of composite material processes of machining with the diamond cutter (ADS) and the abrasive water jet machining (AWJM) are recommended [17-19]. When AWJM is considered, the defects observed are striations on the exit of the water jet and craters on the machined surface. During the machining of metallic materials by AWJ process, authors in [20] have mentioned that these defects are affected mainly by the magnitude and the distribution of the kinetic energy. In addition, other experimental

works [17-19] have shown that the size of streaks increases with the distance from the water jet source. Currently, in the industrial field, during machining of composites materials, the parameter used for qualifying the machined surface is the arithmetic average roughness “Ra”. It is important to state that the “Ra” parameter is initially developed to qualify the machined surfaces of metallic materials. When considering composite materials, there is a conflict about the use of this parameter. Indeed, different works have shown contradictory results. For example, the mechanical tensile tests carried out on unidirectional (UD) samples made of glass fibres and epoxy resin and oriented at + 45 ° relative to the axis of loading [6], have shown that the tensile strength increases with the increase of the average roughness (Ra). However, the compressive mechanical tests conducted on UD specimens oriented at 0° (fibre direction in the same direction of the loading) [21] have shown that the stress failure decreases with the increase of the surface roughness “Ra”. In the work done by [22], the authors have investigated the effect of surface roughness on the quasi-static and fatigue behavior of short fibre reinforced plastics and found that the mechanical behavior (at the macro scale) of the composite part made of short fibres is not affected by the surface roughness.

The authors [23-24] studied a multidirectional CFRP and made a comparison between the different machining processes: abrasive water jet (AWJ) machining, cutting with abrasive diamond cutter (ADS) and edge trimming with polycrystalline diamond (PCD). The authors have found that the abrasive diamond cutter provides better results in terms of roughness and bending mechanical resistance. The PCD specimens gave a good surface roughness (Ra) however they gave the poorest bending mechanical resistance. They also showed without providing extensive comments that the bending mechanical resistance of AWJ samples decreases with the increase of the average surface roughness (Ra).

Therefore, the aim of this work is to investigate on one hand the influence of the trimming processes (conventional and non-conventional machining) on the induced damages and on the other hand the influence of these damages on the mechanical behavior. For this purpose, quasi-static tests (compressive and interlaminar shear tests) and

fatigue tests (tension-tension) have been conducted on different composite specimens obtained with trimming with a burr tool and by ADS cutting process. Quasi-static tests are carried out on specimens obtained by a standard cutting tool (burr tool), an abrasive water jet machining (AWJ) and an abrasive diamond cutter (ADS). During the fatigue tests, an Infrared (IR) camera is used to estimate the endurance limit of the different composite samples. The effect of rectification on the quasi-static and fatigue responses is also investigated.

2 Experimental procedures

2.1. Material Preparation

Carbon-fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) composite of 5.2 mm thickness (20 layers) was used for conducting the trimming study. The CFRP composite was made using unidirectional prepreps supplied by Hexcel Composite Company referenced under T700/M21-GC. The stacking sequence of the laminate is [90/90/-45/0/45/90/-45/ 90/45/90]_S so as to get a multidirectional laminate. This stacking sequence was chosen because it was demonstrated in [25] that edge delamination occur during compression tests .The curing process was then carried out at 180 °C for 120 min during which the pressure was maintained at 7 bar in an autoclave while the vacuum pressure is set to -0.7 bar. The mechanical properties of the ply are summarized in table 1.

Composite Material (T700/M21)	Ply thickness: 0.26 mm, Fibre content: $V_f = 59\%$ Staking sequence with respect to the feed direction: [90/90/-45/0/45/90/-45/ 90/45/90] _S Young modulus: $E_1 = 142$ Gpa, $E_t = 8.4$ Gpa Shear modulus: $G_{12} = 3.8$ Gpa, Glass transition temperature: $T_g = 187$ °C Energy release rates in mode I and II: $G_{IC} = 0.35$ N.mm, $G_{IIC} = 1.21$ N.mm
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Table 1 Summary of the material properties

2.2. Samples preparation

The composite specimens were prepared using three cutting processes, an abrasive water jet (AWJ) a diamond cutter (ADS) and a standard cutting tool.

“JEDO technologies” company conducts the abrasive water jet machining. The machining parameters used were:

- Abrasive particles: 220 mesh,
- Abrasive flow rate: 300 g / min,
- Nozzle diameter: 0.25 mm,
- Jet pressure: 3600 bar (cf. Table 1),
- Feed speeds were chosen, 100 mm / min and 500 mm / min. These two values generate two different surface qualities.

Five specimens were prepared for each cutting condition and for each quasi-static and fatigue mechanical tests.

ADS samples were obtained by a diamond saw (cutter) referenced under «DIAMFORCE JANTE CONTINUE-D100-AL19-GR 427 ». In order to study the impact of the rectification process on the mechanical behavior, some specimens initially obtained by ADS cutting were rectified. In this case a thickness of 0.5 mm is removed from each side of the sample. Also, five specimens were prepared for the compressive quasi-static mechanical test and a specimen is prepared for tensile fatigue test.

The standard cutting tool machining experiments are performed using a “DUBUS” 3-axis milling machine with a maximum spindle speed of 75000 rpm. These experiments were conducted using different cutting conditions. However in this paper only specimens having similar roughness values as the abrasive water jet machining and ADS cutting plus a cutting condition where the surface roughness is very high (poor surface quality) are considered. Samples with similar roughness values are generated by different combinations of cutting speed, feed speed and cutting distance (L_c). Table 2 summarizes the trimming parameters and the experimental details for the specimens tested in quasi-static loading. Two specimens were prepared for fatigue tests. The first one is machined with a new tool with a cutting speed of 700 m/min and a feed speed of 500 mm/min in order to generate a good surface quality. The second specimen is machined by a used tool, after a machining distance of 2.5 m, a cutting speed of 1400 m/min and a feed speed of 125 mm/min were chosen to generate a poor surface quality.

Tool	Tungsten carbide burr tool Diameter: 6 mm
Standard cutting tool machining conditions	V_f : Feed (mm/min) : 125, 250 and 500 N: cutting speed (m/min): 350, 700 and 1400 a_e : Radial depth of cut (mm) : 2
Abrasive Water Jet Machining	Abrasive # 220, diameter d: 67 μ m. Nozzle diameter : 0.25 mm Flow rate of abrasive: 300 g/min. V_f (mm/min): 100, 500. Pression (bar): 3600

Table 2 Tool geometries and trimming conditions.

2.3. Surface defects characterization

The machined surfaces were analyzed using two measurement devices. First a surface roughness tester “Mitutoyo SJ 500” was used to measure the surface roughness, the total measuring length was set to 5 mm to avoid overflowing. The second device is a 3D topographer “Altisurf 520”, which was used to perform the 3D measurements and surface roughnesses without contact. The Altisurf 520 uses the principle of optical microscopy with confocal white light source. The wavelength was analyzed by a focused spectrophotometer analysis that measures the distance between the lens and the surface of the object. The measuring step was set to 4 μ m on both directions x and y. The results obtained with both measurement techniques were then correlated with a scanning electron microscope (SEM) images obtained using a scanning electron microscope “JEOL”.

2.4. Mechanical experiments

a) Static loading

Mechanical quasi-static tests were performed on an MTS 322 tester with hydraulic jaws (Figure 1). The compressive and tensile tests were conducted following the standards AFNOR NF T 51-120-3, NF EN ISO 527-4 and AFNOR NF T 57-104 respectively.

b) Fatigue loading

The fatigue tests were conducted at room temperature using an equipped with hydraulically operated wedge grips. Specimens tested have been instrumented on the surface by an extensometer and an infrared camera.

A FLIR SC5000 infrared camera with a pixel resolution of 320 x 240 and the temperature sensitivity inferior to 20 mK at 30°C at high speed frame rates (1 Hz to 150 Hz) was used to monitor the specimen surface temperature (Fig. 1). For our tests, a frequency of 5 Hz was used to record thermal dissipation. The camera was equipped with an integrated motorized lens and could be easily focused using ALTAIR-LI software. The rectangular plate specimen of the carbon/epoxy composite has an emissivity $\varepsilon = 0.9$.

An extensometer was used to monitor the local strain allowing the calculation of the stiffness degradation of the specimen during the cyclic loading. These axial tension-tension fatigue tests were conducted in a load control environment using a constant amplitude sinusoidal waveform, a loading frequency of 10 Hz and a stress ratio of 0.1 at various maximum applied stress levels. These fatigue tests were conducted in progressive step cyclic loads ranging from 8% to 75% of UTS, each for 10000 cycles.

The IR camera was fixed on a tripod and placed at a distance of 100 cm from the carbon/epoxy composite plate in order to capture stable images without any vibration (figure 1).

From the IR temperature plots it was possible to evaluate the damage evolution and the endurance limit of the specimens [26] (Fig. 1).

The deformation of the structure is usually followed by heat dissipation. When the material is deformed or damaged, a part of the energy necessary to the starting and the propagation of the damage is irreversibly transformed into heat [27-35]. In general, the endurance limit is obtained by Whöler curves (stress vs. cycles). This endurance limit can also be obtained from the temperature stabilization curves [29-30] by intersecting the two straight lines that interpolates the stabilization temperature and the corresponding stress level.

Fig. 1. Experimental procedure for fatigue tests

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Quasi-static tests

Figures 2 show the results of compressive quasi-static stresses obtained for different tests carried out on specimens obtained by the three machining processes and characterized by identical surface roughnesses. From these figures, it is noticed that the samples obtained by AWJ are characterized by higher compressive stresses than those of specimens machined by conventional machining processes (cutting tool or ADS). As an example, for specimens with an average surface roughness “Ra” of 6.4 μm , the compressive strength of specimens machined by AWJ are 21% higher compared to those of specimens machined by the ADS cutting (cf. fig 2).

Fig. 2. Compressive strength vs. surface roughness of different samples obtained by AWJ machining, burr tool machining and ADS cutting.

It is noticed that for the same surface roughness value the discrepancy between the compressive stresses of specimens machined with AWJ and those with burr tool is around of 15%.

Also, it is noticed that the compressive strength of specimens obtained by AWJ is decreasing while increasing the surface roughness. However, for specimens obtained with a conventional machining (burr tool) a random evolution of the compressive strength is observed when increasing the surface roughness value (cf. fig.2).

It is also observed that, smaller standard deviations are obtained when considering samples machined with the AWJ process. This reflects the good repeatability of the machined surfaces with the AWJ process.

The differences in the mechanical behavior could be related to the form of the defects generated during the trimming process of the composite specimens. In fact, some shapes of damages can promote an important stress concentration that leads to the deterioration of mechanical properties.

Figure 3 presents the defects obtained after trimming with conventional machining using a burr tool. It is observed that defects induced by the cutting tool are located mainly at the plies oriented at - 45 ° (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Form of the trimmed surface after machining with burr tool. (a) Image topography 3D. (b) SEM observation.

These defects have the form of wrenched areas with different depths. These depths vary from 30 µm to 70 µm (fig. 4) when the average roughness “Ra”

varies from 6.4 µm to 19.8 µm. In addition these defects can be accompanied with inter-laminar (or intra-laminar) cracks. The presence of these cracks can explain the relatively small values of the compressive strength when considering conventional machining with a burr tool.

Fig. 4. Evolution of the roughness valley (Rv) versus the surface roughness (Ra).

The defects generated after machining with the ADS cutting process have mostly the form of streaks (Fig. 5). These streaks represent wrenched areas and follow the tool trajectory. They are caused by the random distribution of diamond grains with different sizes and shapes on the cutting face of the abrasive diamond cutter (ADS). The trajectory of the defects is linked to the cutting tool trajectory, and the fibre directions do not affect these damages. For this, the ADS defects are observed on the entire machined surface (Fig. 5-b) and the distinction of the different fibre orientations is impossible. The nature of these damages depends mainly of the feed speed (in this case, it is controlled manually by the operator) and the size of diamond grains. This can explain the high standard deviation of the results. The depth of these defects is around 30 µm. This value is smaller compared to those obtained on the trimmed surface by burr tool.

Fig. 5. Machined surface obtained by ADS cutter. (a) 3D topography. (b) SEM observation.

It was also observed that during the machining by AWJ, defects were in the form of streaks and craters, which are independent to the fibre orientation. Streaks appear at the exit of the machined surface and the craters over the entire machined surface (Fig. 6). From the literature review it was mentioned that, the size of the streaks damages (length and width) decrease with the increase of the jet pressure [17-19]. This cutting process occurs by the erosion mechanisms and the produced damages are independent of the fibres orientation (cf. Figure 6-a) and appear periodically all over the surface. Getting repeatable defects all over the surface explains the small standard deviation obtained after the mechanical tests.

Fig.6. Machined surface obtained by abrasive water jet. (a) 3D topography. (b) SEM observation.

In order to investigate the influence of the wrenched damages, five specimens machined by ADS are rectified, in order to remove the wrenched damages and to get a continuous surface, and tested in compressive quasi-static loading.

Figure 7 represent the influence of rectification process on the failure stresses of compressive and inter-laminar shear tests. It is observed that, after the compressive tests, the rectified specimens present a failure stress 10% more compared to specimens without rectification. So the failure stress during compressive tests is strongly influenced by the size of the damages (depth of wrenched areas) induced by the trimming process.

From the Figure 8-b, it is noticed that the rectification process has no influence on the inter-laminar shear strength. It is can assumed that this type of sollicitation is not affected by the wrenched areas defects. This may explain the fact that ADS machining process produces specimens with higher inter-laminar shear strength even with the presence of wrenched areas defects on its machining surfaces.

Fig. 7. Influence of the rectification process of specimens trimmed by ADS process on the compressive strength.

3.2 Fatigue tests

a) Damage analysis

After the fatigue tests, the damage accumulation (D) is calculated. The damage accumulation represents the change in the ratio of dynamic stiffness (E_i) to static stiffness (E_0) and is calculated by the following equation:

$$D = 1 - \frac{E_i}{E_0} \quad (1)$$

The damage profiles versus the normalized cycles (N/Nf, where Nf = 10000 cycles) obtained for a burr tool are shown in Figure 8. From this figure it is noticed that the accumulated damage is inferior to 5% for loads below 24 kN (50% of UTS). When the load reaches 32 kN (67% UTS) the accumulated damage does not exceed 8%. However, when the applied load reaches the 36 kN (75% UTS) the accumulated damages is equal to 12.5%.

Fig. 8. Accumulation of damage obtained for a burr tool specimen under different loading amplitudes versus the normalized cycles (N/Nf)

Similar tendencies were observed when considering the other machining processes specimens. In figure 9, we represent the accumulated damages at the end of cycle for the different processes of machining.

Fig. 9. Evolution of the damage at the end of the loading cycles as a function of the different loading charges.

It is observed that, when considering the load of 36 MPa (75% UTS) the specimen obtained by the ADS process and rectified specimen have the same rate of accumulated damages at the end of the loading cycle (around 8%). However, in the same condition, the trimmed specimens with a burr tool present more important accumulated damages (around 12%). It is also noticed that, whatever the quality of the machining surface after trimming by a burr tool, the accumulated damage of specimens subjected to fatigue test is 50% higher to the accumulated damage of other specimens made of ADS process.

It is important to mention that the average roughness “Ra” obtained by both cutting processes, ADS cutting and by trimming with a burr tool (when the good surface quality is considered) are similar (cf. table 3). In this situation, the fatigue behavior for these specimens is different. In fact, it can be mentioned that, the criteria used today to qualify the quality of the machined surface is not adaptable (e.g., Ra, Sa, etc.) for the case of machining of composite materials.

	Surface Roughness			
	Burr tool – good surface quality	Burr tool – poor surface quality	ADS sample	Rectification
Ra (µm)	8.89±1.71	38.64±6.69	8.87±1.96	1.47±0.16
Rp (µm)	31.34±5.99	127.95±24.7	29.14±8.86	5.27±0.48
Rv (µm)	31.66±8.41	86.88±16.15	28.86±10.15	8.51±3.84
Rz (µm)	63.0±13.04	214.83±37.9	58±18.1	13.77±4.07
Rt (µm)	86.92±23.13	265.69±39.1	74.01±32.19	19.08±7.65

Tab. 3. Surface roughness of all specimens

3.3 Thermography analysis

Figure 10 represents the surface temperature contours recorded by the IR camera during fatigue tests on specimen obtained with a burr tool (specimen with surface roughness Ra = 8.89 µm). From these pictures it is observed that the temperature remains constant throughout the surface for loads less than 16 kN (T = 27~29 °C) (Fig. 10-a). With the increase of loading and until 28 kN, the temperature increases moderately for each step of loading (T = 30~40 °C) (Fig.10 b). However, when the loading is increased by 4 kN to reach 32 kN an important increase of the temperature is noticed (T = 50°C) (Fig.10 c). This temperature continue

increasing highly until the final rupture ($T = 70\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) (Fig. 10 d).

Fig. 10. Temperature contours for specimen machined with burr tool ($R_a = 8.89\text{ }\mu\text{m}$). With cutting speed of 700 m/min, feed speed of 500 mm/min and loading of: (a) 16 kN, (b) 28 kN, (c) 32 kN. (d) 36 kN.

Figure 11 shows the evolution of temperatures for different loads during fatigue tests on specimens machined with burr tool (roughness R_a of $8.89\text{ }\mu\text{m}$). This variation on the temperatures is due to the thermo-elasticity of the material and the friction between the layers (i.e. fibres/fibres and/or fibres/matrix). It is observed that, two stages for the temperature evolution were distinguished. In the first stage, an important increase is observed, in the second stage, the temperature reaches a balance due to the saturation in the damage. With the increase in loading, the rate of the damage and the frictions become more important. This stability is followed by an abrupt increase of the damage and temperature of the specimen corresponding to the rupture [26]. For the final load the saturation is not reached.

Fig. 11. Evolution of temperature as a function of the normalised cycle (N/N_f) for standard cutting tool machining sample.

The evolution of the temperature obtained at the end of the loading cycle as a function of different loads and for different specimens is presented on Figure 12. It is noticed that specimens obtained with a burr tool, have the same behavior and that their maximum temperatures before the total fracture are around $70\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. These temperatures are higher compared to those measured during fatigue tests on specimens machined by ADS process. In this case, a difference around 40% when we consider the ADS specimen without rectification and 23% when we consider the ADS specimen with rectification is obtained.

Fig. 12. Evolution of the temperature at the end of the last cycle in function of the applied loading.

3.4 Endurance Limit Investigation

From the literature review [22], the endurance limit is obtained by Whöler curves (stress vs. cycles). This endurance limit can also be obtained from the temperature stabilization curves [29-30] by intersecting the two straight lines that interpolates the stabilization temperature and the corresponding stress level. The profile of ΔT at 10000 cycles for different loads and for the specimen machined by ADS process represented on the Figure 13. In this situation, the endurance limit is estimated to 198.4 MPa.

$$\Delta T = T_f - T_0 \quad (2)$$

Fig. 13. Temperature variation vs. stresses for the ADS specimen with rectification.

However for rectified ADS specimen the endurance limit is improved by 7.5%. This improvement is even higher when considering the specimen obtained by a burr tool with a surface roughness similar to ADS cutting specimen. In this case a variation of 14% is observed. Even when considering the specimen obtained by a burr tool and having a high surface roughness ($R_a = 38.64 \mu\text{m}$) the endurance limit is higher to ADS cutting (10%) (Fig. 14).

Fig. 14. Endurance limit vs surface roughness for different specimens.

4. Conclusions

In this paper, the effect of machining process, conventional machining (burr tool and abrasive diamond cutter (ADS)) and non conventional machining (abrasive water jet (AWJ)), on the mechanical behavior of composite parts made of carbon/epoxy is investigated. The following conclusion can be drawn:

- 1- The compressive quasi-static tests showed that specimens machined by the AWJ process present a failure stress in compression 10% more important compared to other specimens machined by (ADS and burr tool). Therefore mechanical behavior is highly affected by the choice of the machining process.
- 2- The same surface roughness parameters (R_a , R_p , R_v , act.) can be obtained by different machining processes. However the form of the defects is completely different from one machining process to another.
- 3- The rectification process conducted on specimens trimmed by ADS process confirmed that the removal of the wrenched areas improve the compressive strength.
- 4- The Fatigue tests carried out on various specimens trimmed by different machining processes show that the higher endurance limit corresponds to those trimmed by a burr tool. This result remains true for any quality of the machined surface. In addition, we have noticed that the rectification process improves the endurance limit of ADS specimens (7.5%).

5- The results above confirm that surface roughness criteria are not recommended for the machining of composite materials. It had been seen that specimens obtained by a burr tool and with different levels of surface quality ($R_a = 8 \mu\text{m}$, $R_a = 38 \mu\text{m}$), offer similar results of the endurance limit. In addition, the specimens obtained by the ADS process offer a lower endurance limit (15%) for the same surface roughness as specimens trimmed by the burr tool process.

6- The compressive quasi-static tests showed a higher compressive strength for ADS specimens, however, in tensile-tensile fatigue test, the specimens machined by a burr tool have the highest endurance limit. Therefore in addition to the machining process, the type or even the mode of mechanical loading can affect highly the mechanical response.

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